

Subject-Specific and COM Acceleration-Enhanced Reflex Neuromuscular Model to Predict Ankle Responses in Perturbed Gait

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Abstract—Subject-specific musculoskeletal models generate more accurate joint torque estimates from electromyography (EMG) inputs in relation to experimentally obtained torques. Similarly, reflex Neuromuscular Models (NMMs) that employ COM states in addition to musculotendon information generate muscle activations to musculoskeletal models that better predict ankle torques during perturbed gait. In this study, the reflex NMM of locomotion of one subject is identified by employing an EMG-calibrated musculoskeletal model in unperturbed and perturbed gait. A COM acceleration-enhanced reflex NMM is identified. Subject-specific musculoskeletal models improve torque tracking of the ankle joint in unperturbed and perturbed conditions. COM acceleration-enhanced reflex NMM improves ankle torque tracking especially in early stance and during backward perturbation. Results found herein can guide the implementation of reflex controllers in active prosthetic and orthotic devices.

I. INTRODUCTION

During stance, ankle responses are important stabilizing mechanisms during legged locomotion. In the onset of a pelvis perturbation, the ankle joint reacts by counteracting the action of perturbation and moving the center of mass (COM) trajectory back to its expected value [1][2].

Ankle responses during locomotion are believed to be coordinated largely by spinal reflexes. In a reflex NMM, dorsiflexor muscles are typically controlled by stretch reflexes and suppressed by dorsiflexor muscle forces, whereas plantar flexors are controlled by force feedback loops [3], [4]. During perturbed locomotion, where a perturbation is applied at the pelvis in the anterior-posterior direction, the aforementioned muscle states feedback does not generate counteracting effects, on the contrary, it amplifies such reactions, with potentially unstabilizing effects. In those perturbed conditions, reflex models of ankle muscle activations that use the COM velocity information are shown to predict biological responses more accurately [5][6][7].

Previous attempts at modeling reflexes do so by using generalized musculoskeletal models, and they identify reflexes that either generate stable locomotion in forward simulations or by trying to minimize the discrepancy between experimental and model output torques. Identifying subjects' musculotendon parameters improves the representativeness of such models, therefore better predicting biological responses [8], with potentially beneficial consequences in their

usage for control.

Reflexes are also used as the basis for control of prosthetic and orthotic devices [9][7][10][11][12]. The usage of such models aids in the generation of biomimetic responses that are geared towards stumble recovery to drive the control of active devices. The usage of COM state feedback in modeling ankle responses and subsequently using those models to drive ankle exoskeletons helps reduce muscle activity during perturbed walking [7].

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of muscle-tendon unit (MTU) parameter calibration in a reflex modeling framework. To that end, electromyography (EMG) of the calf muscles was used to calibrate a musculoskeletal model in treadmill walking at different speeds [13][14]. From such calibrated models, reflex NMMs with the center of mass acceleration and velocity are optimized.

This study is the first to propose a complete reflex formulation that incorporates force/stretch feedback, reciprocal inhibition, and automated identification of MTU parameters from experimental data, making the formulation person and muscle-specific. Furthermore, the novel inclusion of COM acceleration can be a driver for quick responses for orthotic and prosthetic devices.

II. METHODS

A. Data Processing Pipeline

Based on a dataset from [2][1], the data processing pipeline can be divided into four steps:

- 1) An OpenSim [15] gait2392 model is scaled based on marker data, and muscle parameters are scaled by the method described in [16].
- 2) Muscle parameters are further calibrated in the CEINMS toolbox [17] based on EMG inputs.
- 3) A reflex model to drive the muscles of the ankle joint is optimized to minimize model and experimental torque errors.
- 4) Finally, the calibrated musculoskeletal and reflex models are used to estimate ankle joint torques in diverse perturbed and unperturbed conditions.

The implications of not calibrating muscle parameters (step 2) are investigated in order to justify its inclusion. The reflex model optimization in step 3 is repeated for three different reflex structures: default reflex model, COM velocity, and COM acceleration-enhanced model.

B. Dataset

This study is based on data collected by Vlutters et al. [2]. Healthy participants performed treadmill walking on a

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split-belt instrumented treadmill (custom Y-Mill, Motekforce Link, Culemborg, The Netherlands). Interaction forces were independently collected by two 6-DOF force plates (3D forces and moments) on both sides of the treadmill.

Subjects were attached to a perturbation device through a connecting rod fixated to a hip brace that allowed side or rear contact. The perturbation device consists of two motors (SMH60, Moog, Nieuw-Vennep, The Netherlands). Perturbation forces were measured and recorded through a load cell (model QLA131, FUTEK, Los Angeles, CA, USA) in line with each connecting rod.

Subject kinematics were collected through a motion capture system (Visualeyez II, Phoenix Technologies, Burnaby, Canada). Trials consisted of unperturbed and perturbed trials at slow and fast speeds proportional to the subjects' leg length. In each trial, perturbation onset was randomized, with 6 to 12 s between perturbations, and perturbation intensity was either 4, 8, 12 and 16% of subjects body weight, randomly generated. Perturbations were applied at the toe-off right for a duration of 150ms.

Electromyography (EMG) data were collected bilaterally (Bagnoli, Delsys Inc, Natick, MA, USA) for the tibialis anterior (TA), gastrocnemius medialis (GASMED), and other muscles.

This study is based on walking data of one subject of 66kg body weight walking at 2.2km/h. For the calibration of MTU parameters, walking data at 4.2km/h is used as well.

C. Musculoskeletal Model

The Musculoskeletal model simulates the ankle joint, and it is composed of four muscles, namely the tibialis anterior (TA), soleus (SOL), gastrocnemius medialis (GASMED), and gastrocnemius lateralis (GASLAT). The model is implemented in the CEINMS toolbox [17].

EMG and measured joint angles are inputs to the model, which in turn calculates internal states, such as muscle internal lengths and forces, finally resulting in an estimate of joint torques.

Three EMG channels are used to drive the model muscles. TA and SOL are driven by channels S_{TA} and S_{GAS} , respectively, whereas GASLAT and GASMED are driven by S_{GAS} . As GASMED and GASLAT are bi-articular muscles, the ankle and knee joint angles are inputs to the model.

D. Default Reflex Model (RD)

Three different structures for reflex NMMs are explored in this work: a default reflex NMM (RD), a center of mass velocity (RV), and a center of mass acceleration (RA) enhanced NMM in combination with an EMG-calibrated musculoskeletal model. All these models are implemented in CEINMS.

The reflex model generates muscle activation outputs from the musculoskeletal model's internal states. Reflex pathways that generate synthetic muscles activation channels S_{TA} , S_{SOL} , and S_{GAS} are calculated as described in [3].

Reflex model outputs are filtered by a low pass, second order Butterworth filter with a cutoff frequency of 6Hz.

E. COM State added Reflex Model (RV and RA)

COM state-enhanced reflex models add COM velocity (RV) [6][7], and this work proposes to add acceleration (RA) to the reflex equations during the stance phase. Equations 1a to 1c are added to channels S_{TA} , S_{SOL} , and S_{GAS} , respectively.

$$S_{COM,TA,st} = G_{COMTA,st}(\Delta V_{COM}(t_m))^{th_{TA}} \quad (1a)$$

$$S_{COM,SOL,st} = G_{COMSOL,st}(\Delta V_{COM}(t_m))^{th_{SOL}} \quad (1b)$$

$$S_{COM,GAS,st} = G_{COMGAS,st}(\Delta V_{COM}(t_m))^{th_{GAS}} \quad (1c)$$

Inputs from COM states are delayed by 15ms ($t_m = t - 15ms$). The center of mass velocity deviation is calculated as $\Delta V_{COM}(t_m) = (V_{COM}(t_m) - V_{COM,exp}(t_m))$, where V_{COM} is the velocity of the COM in the anterior-posterior direction, and $V_{COM,exp}$ is the expected COM velocity. Expected velocity values are obtained by averaging the COM velocity across all gait cycles of an unperturbed walking trial.

Expected COM velocity values are obtained by estimating the position of the gait cycle as determined by ground reaction forces and segmented between subsequent heel strikes, as shown in Figure 1.

The center of mass deviation is considered different than zero if it overcomes a threshold th , as described in equation 2, and it takes different values for each muscle target (th_{MUSCLE}). The resulting term is multiplied by gain terms relating the data source to the activation channel ($G_{SOURCE\ TARGET}$) during the stance phase of the gait cycle (st)

Equations for RA are analogous to those of RV, and can be easily obtained by switching COM velocities by accelerations.

$$(\Delta V_{COM}(t_m))^{th} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |\Delta V_{COM}| < th \\ \Delta V_{COM} - th & \text{if } V_{COM} > th \\ \Delta V_{COM} + th & \text{if } V_{COM} < -th \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

F. Uncalibrated Reflex Model (RU)

In order to illustrate the impact of the musculoskeletal model calibration, a reflex model is optimized by utilizing a scaled musculoskeletal model, therefore skipping step 2 described in section II-A.

G. Musculoskeletal Model Scaling

An OpenSim gait2392 model is scaled based on marker data, and it is subsequently readjusted by the method proposed by Modenese et. al. [16]. The resulting model has proportional body segments and muscle parameters adapted to individuals. However, muscle isometric force is not adjusted.

Fig. 1. Expected (dashed line), actual (dotted line), and delta (solid line) of COM velocity (right) and acceleration (left). Deltas are the difference between the actual and expected COM state values. Conditions are unperturbed (blue), perturbed forward (yellow), and perturbed backward (red). The shaded area indicates the period of application of the perturbation.

H. Musculoskeletal Model Calibration

The CEINMS toolbox [17] is used to calibrate muscle parameters. In it, muscle parameters are altered to minimize model torque output error in comparison with experimental torques, obtained by inverse dynamics.

Recorded EMGs and kinematics drive the model. EMG data from GASLAT and TA muscles are available. During calibration, EMG from GASLAT drives the SOL, GASMED, and GASLAT, while TA EMG data is used to drive TA. In this step, the EMG shape factor, tendon slack length, optimal fiber length, and muscle maximal isometric force are adjusted [17].

Five seconds of data from unperturbed trials at speeds of 2.2 and 4.3km/h each are used. Furthermore, 2 seconds of null data are used, in which all joint angles, muscle activations, and joint torques are zero. The latter is intended to guarantee that zero EMG inputs will generate zero muscle forces and joint torques.

I. Reflex Optimization

Reflex models RD, RV, RA, and RU are optimized by altering reflex model parameters in order to minimize the cost function 3e, composed by a normalized torque RMSE term (e_t) and an activation penalty term (p_t) for each trial t with N samples, for a total of T trials considered in the optimization process. Torque error terms are defined as the difference between experimental, inverse dynamics (T_{ID}) and model output torques (T_{model}). The weighting term w_p was defined heuristically to make muscle activation penalties large enough such that activations are spread across all channels.

$$\tilde{T}_{ID}(k) = \frac{T_{ID}(k)}{\max_l |T_{ID}(l)|} \quad (3a)$$

$$\tilde{T}_{model}(k) = \frac{T_{model}(k)}{\max_l |T_{ID}(l)|} \quad (3b)$$

$$e_t = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N (\tilde{T}_{ID}(k) - \tilde{T}_{model}(k))^2}{N}} \quad (3c)$$

$$p_t = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{S_{TA}^2(k) + S_{SOL}^2(k) + S_{GAS}^2(k)}{3N} \quad (3d)$$

$$c = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{e_t + w_p p_t}{T} \quad (3e)$$

Average responses are obtained for each condition by averaging out all data types (joint angles, torques, etc) by all trials of the same type (perturbed backward from 16 to 4% of body weight, unperturbed, perturbed forward from 4 to 16% of body weight), for a total of 9 categories. Gait cycles whose times are 2 standard deviations from the average are excluded. These averaged responses are used to calibrate all reflex models.

RD is optimized based on unperturbed data, as previous works have demonstrated that it cannot accurately track joint torques in perturbed gait [6][7], and the inclusion of perturbed data degrades its tracking of unperturbed data. Conversely, RV and RA are optimized with unperturbed and perturbed data at the extreme perturbation values, namely 16% of body weight in either direction, for a total of 3 conditions.

The CMA-ES algorithm provided by the Pagmo 2 library [18] is used to optimize reflex parameters for a maximum of 200 generations and 25 individuals per generation.

Gain and offset parameters are optimized for RD. RV and RA utilize the optimization results from RD, and build upon them to adjust gains (G) and thresholds (th) of equations 1a to 1c only.

III. RESULTS

A. Muscle Calibration

Musculotendon calibration resulted in parameters that lie within physiologically feasible boundaries. RMSE between experimental and model torque is 12.02 Nm ($\sigma = 2.18$ Nm). Torque tracking discrepancies between heel strike (gait cycle = 0) and foot flat (gait cycle ≈ 0.1) occur due to the unmatched timing of TA activation.

The absence of EMG data from the SOL muscle partially justifies deviation during mid-stance (gait cycle from ≈ 0.2

to ≈ 0.35), and the absence of sufficient dorsiflexion torque after toe-off (gait cycle ≈ 0.65) can again be attributed to the timing of TA activation.

B. Reflex Optimization

The optimization of RD NMM took an average of 2.12s per generation, for a total optimization time of 423s, whereas the COM Velocity enhanced NMM took an average of 3.42s per iteration, for a total of 683s. Resulting gains lie in the range between -1 and 1.5, offsets are between 0 and 1, and thresholds between 0 and 1.2.

1) *Consequences of Calibrating Muscle Models With EMG*: A generic musculoskeletal model can be used in conjunction with a reflex model to generate activations. It has been observed that, in such cases, the lack of dorsiflexion torque in early stance is even more pronounced (Figure 2).

The activations of SOL and GAS match those of experimental EMGs in timing, but the discrepancy between the subject's musculoskeletal characteristics and its model naturally makes the intensity of such muscles distinct. The activation of TA, on the other hand, is entirely absent from RU. It is important to note that the optimization was restarted several times with different starting conditions, and in all cases, the optimizer selected a solution that did not include TA activation.

The RMSE error in unperturbed and perturbed backward conditions are reduced by calibrating the MTU models with EMGs, as shown in Table I. A significance level of 0.05 was not reached for forward perturbations.

Fig. 2. Biological (blue, dashed) and model torque responses of the ankle joint in unperturbed condition for uncalibrated (red) and calibrated (yellow) reflex models.

2) *Default Reflex NMM (RD)*: During unperturbed conditions, the main discrepancy between NMM and experimental torque occurs between heel strike and foot flat. Experimental results show higher dorsiflexion torque for a longer period of time, softening the excursion of the foot to the ground.

In the perturbed cases, RD generates less stance plantarflexion (PF) torque and when the subject is pushed backward, RD generates as much or more torque in the PF direction, as shown in Figure 3, which displays ankle torques for unperturbed and perturbed gaits with an intensity 16% of body weight in either direction. This is the opposite of that expected from biological responses, which is potentially destabilizing.

Perturbed data has not been employed in the calibration of RD, thus it is not expected to accurately track torques in such conditions. This is done as adding perturbed data to the training of RD does not significantly improve tracking in perturbed conditions, and it degrades tracking performance in unperturbed conditions.

3) *COM Velocity and Acceleration-Enhanced Reflex NMMs (RV and RA)*: During unperturbed conditions, RV performs worse than RD. That happens as there are sporadic excursions of the center of mass velocity beyond the threshold th during unperturbed gaits. During perturbed gaits, RV better track experimental data compared to RD. Such behavior is propitiated by a modulation of S_{TA} and S_{GAS} channels. S_{GAS} gets activated more intensely during the stance phase when pushed forward and gets suppressed when the perturbation is in the opposite direction. Conversely, S_{TA} is less prevalent in mid-stance when the subject is perturbed forward, and it gets activated more intensely when perturbed backward.

Adding acceleration to the reflex NMM improves torque tracking in unperturbed and backward perturbed gaits. Unlike velocity, however, its more significant influence occurs while the perturbation is active. COM acceleration feedback performs better in the backward perturbation direction, such that PF torque is reduced as plantar flexor muscles are suppressed. Interestingly, TA is also largely deactivated during perturbations of this type.

IV. DISCUSSION

The main methodological distinctions in relation to [6] are (1) the inclusion of activation penalty terms in the cost function, (2) the normalization of trials cost by maximum torque, and (3) the optimization of COM state threshold th .

Muscle calibration results are in line with those observed in other studies. Ankle torque RMSE errors obtained from this step (0.1821 ± 0.033 Nm/kg) are within the margins of error reported by similar studies, which describe a maximum RMSE error of 0.37 ± 0.12 Nm/kg [13].

In unperturbed conditions, reflex model calibration results are close to those reported in related works, as displayed in Table II. RMSE error averages obtained in this work are lower in unperturbed conditions. Perturbed conditions are not reported separately in [7], but averaging forward and backward conditions obtained in this work yield 0.1996 Nm/Kg, which closely approximates the results described therein. RD shows a significant improvement in tracking ankle torques in unperturbed conditions, but degrades its tracking capacity in perturbed gaits, with an average of 0.22425 Nm/Kg, as perturbed data is not used to optimize it.

RMSE errors reported in [7] are slightly lower than those obtained here. In particular, a big variability of results is seen in forward perturbations, indicating that the subject displayed a variable response to this kind of perturbation, once all controllers show the same behavior. For other conditions, RMSE errors are up to 12% higher.

TABLE I
RMSE ERROR FOR ALL CONTROLLERS EXPLORED IN THIS WORK. ALL TESTS PERFORMED IN RELATION TO RD.

Controller	Pert. BW			Unperturbed			Pert. FW		
	μ	σ	p	μ	σ	p	μ	σ	p
RU	9.4983	3.2164	0.0130	12.1126	4.2753	<0.001	16.8483	12.4894	0.7932
RD	12.9456	4.9249	-	7.2178	3.2288	-	16.6587	11.4909	-
RV	8.9570	1.5606	0.0188	8.9927	5.0540	<0.001*	12.0184	11.5251	<0.001
RA	8.5814	3.4917	0.0426	7.5905	3.2308	<0.001*	16.2564	11.7201	0.6931*

* Data not normally distributed

Fig. 3. Ankle torque responses in perturbed backward (left), unperturbed (center), and perturbed forward (right) conditions with intensities of 16% of body weight for RD, RV, and RA controllers. Shaded areas indicate the application of perturbation.

TABLE II
RMSE ERROR NORMALIZED BY SUBJECT WEIGHT (NM/KG) IN
COMPARISON WITH [7], FROM WHICH GRAPH DATA IS EXTRACTED.

Source	Pert. BW		Unperturbed		Pert. FW	
	†	[7]	†	[7]	†	[7]
RU	0.1439	0.2153*	0.1835	0.1575	0.2553	0.2153*
RD	0.1961	-	0.1094	-	0.2524	-
RV	0.1357	0.1256*	0.1363	0.1216	0.1821	0.1256*

† Results obtained in this work.

* Average between backward and forward condition provided.

DF torques consistently fall short of the reference for all controllers observed. The foot is slightly plantarflexed at the heel strike, and it plantarflexes further until foot flat is achieved. DF torque peaks at the same time as foot flat is achieved. The activity of PF muscles in early stance offsets this force, and as PF muscles are capable of providing more torque than TA, DF torque does not reach high enough values. In the early stance, RD, RV, RA, and RC compensate for the weak recorded TA by providing more TA activation than measured experimentally.

Although utilizing a generalized musculoskeletal model generates fair torque tracking performance, there is a significant improvement when subject-specific parameters are employed. However, the consistent underestimation of peak torques in RU favors the condition where perturbations in the backward direction are applied, as it is in line with the biological response of a backward perturbation. In unperturbed conditions, torque RMSE errors for RD are more than 40% lower when compared with RU, and the variability between gait cycles is also reduced.

COM Velocity after perturbation remains distant from the expected trajectory during most of the gait cycle, having its biggest impact during late stance. That in part explains why COM velocity feedback is better at modulating torques at

these periods of the gait cycle. COM Acceleration, on the other hand, has its biggest effect during the application of perturbation. This explains how the tracking of perturbed gaits at the same interval is significantly improved. RA displays improved torque tracking during backward perturbations, but the RMSE reductions in forward perturbed gait do not reach significance. The effectiveness of RA and RV in different time windows of the gait cycle can be explored in a controller that combines both techniques.

A. Limitations of this study

No EMG from the SOL muscle has been used for the calibration of MTU parameters. SOL is usually active earlier in the gait cycle if compared to GAS, thus its inclusion would assist in more accurate and realistic identification of muscle parameters, especially when it relates to predicting early stance responses. Furthermore, other studies have indicated that smoothing the transition between the parameter sets of gains used in swing and stance can improve torque tracking even further [7]. Such a technique has not been attempted in this study. Moreover, controllers proposed in this study are optimized by following experimental kinematics and minimizing joint torques with no concern with bipedal walking stability, therefore not guaranteeing the same. This approach has been shown to successfully drive an ankle exoskeleton [7], which provides a fraction of the total power of locomotion. Therefore, the application of this type of controller in prosthetic devices might require more careful consideration of stability by taking the forward dynamics of the movement into account. Lastly, this study is based on data from one user. By including more subjects in the analysis, it is possible to more confidently assert if the observations made here are valid across a wider spectrum of individuals.

B. Potential Applications

The controllers proposed in this study may be implemented into prosthetic and orthotic devices.

V. CONCLUSION

This study explored subject-specific reflex NMMs and a COM acceleration feedback-enhanced reflex NMM for more accurate torque tracking of ankle torque responses during perturbed conditions. We show that the calibration of muscle parameters based on EMGs improves the subsequent reflex model calibration. Furthermore, COM acceleration-enhanced reflex models also contain information capable of improving torque tracking performance during perturbed conditions. This type of feedback has the characteristic of responding more promptly to external perturbations, which culminates in quick torque responses. Both developments can benefit the implementation of reflex controllers into prosthetic and orthotic devices.

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